

Dive into the Future of Museum Data!

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Get ready to unlock the secrets behind skills, requirements, and training for museum data curators! On April 17th, the Natural History Museum Vienna (NHMW) hosted a groundbreaking workshop on data curation essentials, which was co-organised by Heimo Rainer (NHMW) and Nikos Gänsdorfer, working for the [Skills4EOSC](#) project, and Sabine Fauland, coordinator of the Austrian Association of Museums ([Museumsbund](#)). Representatives from museums and collections from across Austria came together to discuss open science, FAIR principles, and data management practices.

Curious about the game-changing insights and innovative ideas discussed? Keep reading to uncover the keys to professional museum data curation!

The workshop “Digital Curators in Museums and Collections” commenced with setting the stage for a day of insightful exploration. Valuable context was then provided to explain the significance of data stewardship and curation in museums within the broader framework of EOSC and the Skills4EOSC project.

A dynamic panel discussion ensued, in which topics spanned from enhancing data visibility within museum collections to grappling with the challenges of digital transformation. Participants also discussed the complexities of data documentation, trust in data, and the evolving landscape of data management.

In smaller breakout groups, attendees engaged in lively discourse on four key themes: data handling and practices, Open Science in general, basics in data management, FAIR and Open Science and, last but not least, actual data management practices. Each group fervently explored two of those topics over 20-minute sessions, culminating in comprehensive presentations of their findings to all present. Two key points were discussed in all of the groups:

First, data curators must possess many skills. For example, they need the technical know-how to be able to curate data, while also being able to understand the (scientific) discipline in which data is to be curated. Apart from this, legal knowledge (licenses, handling sensitive data) and soft skills, in the sense of communication, are necessary. The latter matters in particular because data curators operate at interfaces and must facilitate the exchange between different groups of experts.

Second, in order to anchor data management, efficient Open Science practices and FAIR principles institutionally, not only is commitment from the management level required, but also a bottom-up approach. In this respect, discussions between different levels must take place in order to finally obtain feedback from the users of the data - such as researchers. Ultimately, however, all strategies can only be successful if networking and cooperation are made possible beyond the boundaries of organizations and countries.

Thanks to this event, the prerequisites for someone working as data curator or data steward with regard to collections became much clearer. Nonetheless, more work on the topic and detailed discussions is ahead to define the minimum skill set, either for Master courses or training on the job.